

Redox Potential Studies during the Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Oxalic, Malonic and Tartaric Acids Induced by Potassium Permanganate

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The changes in e.m.f. were noted during the reaction in a mixture containing 0.1 M acid and 0.01 M mercuric chloride and potassium permanganate each at 30°C. The time of just appearance of mercurous chloride precipitate was noted down visually as the "Induction period". The experiments were repeated at different temperatures and concentrations of the reactants. Similar results were obtained. The observations obtained at 30°C are shown in the figure.

Fig. 1

It is seen from the figure (curve a) that in the case of oxalic acid the e.m.f. of the system first falls gradually and then rapidly till there is a sharp break at which it remains constant for a short interval, thereafter it again falls continuously. It is interesting to note that the sharp break in the e.m.f. time-curve occurs at the time at which the reduction of mercuric chloride just starts as observed visually (10 minutes) and the total fall in e.m.f. from the beginning upto this stage is 0.405 volts.

Curve (b) shows that in the case of malonic acid the e.m.f. falls first slowly and then rapidly till it reaches a minimum. After this, it shows a small rise and then again falls continuously. The total fall in e.m.f. up to the end of induction period (8.5 minutes) as observed visually, is 0.395 volts.

In the case of tartaric acid (curve c) there is no break in the curve but a continuous S shaped curve is obtained. In this case the precipitation of calomel just appeared (induction period 8 minutes) when the system had recorded a fall of 0.425 volts in e.m.f.

Neither organic acid (oxalic, malonic or tartaric) nor KMnO_4 alone reduces mercuric chloride but a mixture of the two does so. This clearly suggests that as a result of interaction of the two ions (i.e. anion of the acid and MnO_4^-), some active product is produced which reduces mercuric chloride to mercurous chloride, as has been suggested in our previous publications¹. The time required for the production of this active product (or in other words, the time, after the mixing of the reactants, at which the precipitation of calomel just starts) has been termed as the period of induction.

From the above studies it is revealed that the total fall in potential during the induction period is almost the same in all the cases irrespective of the nature of the acid used, concentration of the reactants and temperature. This indicates that heptavalent manganese is reduced to the same valence state before the reduction of mercuric chloride by oxalic, malonic and tartaric acids in presence of potassium permanganate as inductor, just starts.

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1. Bansal, O. P. and Mathur, P. C., *this Journal*, 1965; 42, 232, 235; 1966, 43, 215.